

ABSORPTION OF IODINE BY HYDROXYLAMINE SALTS. PART I. STUDY OF THE REACTION

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In the reaction of iodine with hydroxylamine it appears that at least two types of reactions proceed simultaneously, one involving absorption and the other, liberation of iodine. Titrations show that the amount of iodine absorbed always reaches a maximum after which the absorption distinctly diminishes. In neutral solution, the liberation of iodine takes place slowly and apparently reaches a definite value in fifteen to thirty minutes. Nitrite appears to be the chief product of the reaction. This is supported by the fact that the maximum amount of iodine absorbed tends to approximate to four atoms of iodine for one molecule of hydroxylamine and never exceeds this limit.

Although various investigations (Meyeringh, *Ber.*, 1877, 10, 1940; Haga, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1887, 51, 794; Jones and Carpenter, *ibid.*, 1903, 83, 1394; Erwin, Rupp and Mader, *Arch. Phar.*, 1913, 251, 295; Bray, Simpson and Mackenzie, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 1363; Raschig, "Schwefel-und-stickstoff studien", 1924, p. 183; Olander, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 129, 1) have tried to work out a suitable method for the volumetric estimation of hydroxylamine based on the absorption of iodine, neither a satisfactory standard method has been evolved nor does the course of the reaction appear to have been studied. Meyeringh (*loc. cit.*) represented the reaction involved as

Haga (*loc. cit.*), however, reported that the above method was unsatisfactory, because the amount of iodine absorbed was found to depend on (i) the concentration of the solution, (ii) the presence of the sodium salts and (iii) the presence of carbonic anhydride. Jones and Carpenter (*loc. cit.*) state "in basic solutions about three atoms of iodine were required for one molecule of hydroxylamine." According to Erwin, Rupp and Mader (*loc. cit.*) the quantity of iodine absorbed depends on (i) the nature and the quantity of the material used to absorb hydriodic acid and (ii) the time during which the reaction mixture is allowed to stand. Bray, Simpson and Mackenzie (*loc. cit.*) suggested an empirical method. Endress and Kaufmann (*Annalen*, 1937, 530, 184) have evolved a method for a micro-estimation of hydroxylamine in concentrations of 0.1 to 0.2 × 10⁻⁶ g. of NH₂OH in 10 c.c., the HNO₂ formed may then be determined photometrically by the diazo method, the error being ± 2 to 3 %.

When the absorption of iodine by hydroxylamine is measured, the results widely vary being governed by (i) the time of reaction, (ii) temperature and (iii) the acidity of the solution. When a neutral solution of hydroxylamine salt is oxidised by means of iodine, nitrite seems to be the main product of reaction, though nitrate is also detected in minute traces. The reaction appears to take place in two stages:—

As the nitrate is found to be present only in traces, it is reasonable to assume that the final product of oxidation of hydroxylamine by iodine can be nitrous acid only. The

presence of traces of nitrate may be due to the oxidation of nitrous acid by atmospheric oxygen or it may have been formed by auto-oxidation thus :

Primary and Secondary Reactions.—When titrations were carried out under different experimental conditions, the quantity of iodine absorbed was found to vary considerably with (i) concentration of the hydroxylamine salt, (ii) quantity of iodine added, (iii) temperature and (iv) time, although the quantity of hydroxylamine taken remained the same. It has been shown in what follows that in the oxidation of hydroxylamine, there must be at least two types of reactions going on simultaneously, once the reaction has started. It appears that in the beginning the primary reactions, shown by the following equations :

are faster than the secondary reactions shown by the following equations :

It can be seen that during secondary reactions iodine is liberated, while during primary reactions iodine is absorbed.

Effect of Time.—From Table I it appears that the amount of iodine absorbed always reached a maximum in about 2 to 10 minutes in neutral solutions showing that up to this point iodine was being absorbed. After the maximum was reached the secondary reactions set in and the amount of iodine absorbed decreased with increase in time until in about 30 minutes the speed of the two reactions was almost the same, except that the secondary reactions preponderated to a small extent.

TABLE I

Vol. of *N*/100 iodine soln. absorbed at 35° by 5 c.c. soln. of *M*/100-NH₂OH.HCl at different dilutions with respect to time when 25 c.c. of *N*/100 iodine solution were added every time.

Time.	Dilution			Time.	Dilution		
	50 c.c.	200 c.c.	500 c.c.		50 c.c.	200 c.c.	500 c.c.
1 min.	9.75 c.c.	14.0 c.c.	17.3 c.c.	10 min.	6.90 c.c.	17.6 c.c.	19.4 c.c.
3	10.40	17.0	19.3	15	6.40	17.1	19.3
5	9.40	17.9	19.5	30	6.00	16.0	19.3

Similar results were obtained with hydroxylamine sulphate and hydroxylamine nitrate under the above experimental conditions.

Effect of Dilution on the Absorption of Iodine.—In neutral solution the amount of iodine absorbed went on increasing as the dilution was increased up to a certain limit as shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Vol. of *N*/100 iodine soln. absorbed at 35° by 5 c.c. soln. of hydroxylamine salts in 5 minutes at different dilutions when 25 c.c. of *N*/100 iodine solution were added every time.

Dilution.	NH ₂ OH.HCl <i>M</i> /100	(NH ₂ OH) ₂ . H ₂ SO ₄ <i>M</i> /200	NH ₂ OH. HNO ₃ <i>M</i> /100	Dilution.	NH ₂ OH.HCl <i>M</i> /100	(NH ₂ OH) ₂ . H ₂ SO ₄ <i>M</i> /200	NH ₂ OH. HNO ₃ <i>M</i> /100
10 c.c.	6.4 c.c.	7.1 c.c.	0.85 c.c.	350 c.c.	19.4 c.c.	18.35 c.c.	18.35 c.c.
25	6.7	7.2	7.05	500	19.5	18.90	19.25
50	9.4	10.4	9.20	750	20.0	20.00	19.90
100	17.9	14.15	14.30	1000	20.0	20.00	20.00
200	19.3	17.95	17.65				

A maximum absorption of iodine occurred with a concentration of 1/50 mol. per litre, at 1/320 mol. per litre and at 1/200 mol. per litre respectively for hydroxylamine hydrochloride, sulphate and nitrate as shown above.

Effect of the amount of Iodine on its Absorption.—In neutral solution as shown in Table III, though the amount of iodine absorbed increased as the quantity of iodine initially added was increased, the amount of iodine absorbed became constant when the quantity of iodine initially added was twice the maximum absorption.

TABLE III

Vol. of *N*/100 iodine soln. absorbed at 35° by 5 c.c. soln. of hydroxylamine salts in 5 minutes at 200 c.c. dilution when different amounts of iodine soln. were added every time.

Vol. of <i>N</i> /100-I ₂ soln.	NH ₂ OH. HCl <i>M</i> /100	(NH ₂ OH) ₂ . H ₂ SO ₄ <i>M</i> /200	NH ₂ OH. HNO ₃ <i>M</i> /100	Vol. of <i>N</i> /100-I ₂ soln.	NH ₂ OH. HCl <i>M</i> /100	(NH ₂ OH) ₂ . H ₂ SO ₄ <i>M</i> /200	NH ₂ OH. HNO ₃ <i>M</i> /100
5 c.c.	5.0 c.c.	5.00 c.c.	5.00 c.c.	25 c.c.	17.7 c.c.	17.95 c.c.	17.65 c.c.
10	10.0	10.00	10.00	35	17.9	17.95	17.90
20	16.8	17.00	16.85	50	17.9	18.95	17.90

Effect of Temperature on the Reaction.—The rate of reaction increased with rise in temperature and *vice versa*. At 45° it was almost three times the quantity absorbed at 0°. It was not possible to continue the observations given below in Table IV, as above this temperature losses due to volatilisation of iodine became appreciable and anomalous results were obtained.

TABLE IV

Vol. of *N*/100 iodine soln. absorbed at different temp. by 5 c.c. soln. of hydroxylamine salts in 5 minutes at 200 c.c. dilution when 25 c.c. of *N*/100 iodine soln. were added every time.

Temp.	NH ₂ OH. HCl <i>M</i> /100	(NH ₂ OH) ₂ . H ₂ SO ₄ <i>M</i> /200	NH ₂ OH. HNO ₃ <i>M</i> /100	Temp.	NH ₂ OH. HCl <i>M</i> /100	(NH ₂ OH) ₂ . H ₂ SO ₄ <i>M</i> /200	NH ₂ OH. HNO ₃ <i>M</i> /100
5°	8.6 c.c.	8.95 c.c.	5.00 c.c.	35°	17.7 c.c.	17.95 c.c.	17.65 c.c.
15	11.4	12.95	13.65	45	18.3	18.55	18.00
25	15.7	17.10	16.40				

All reactions were carried out at a constant temperature in 500 c.c. glass stoppered bottles which were kept in a constant temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) water-bath fitted with an electric thermo-regulator and a stirrer. An excess of iodine was added to the hydroxylamine salt solution and the excess of free iodine was titrated back with standard sodium thiosulphate solution.

Detection and Estimation of the Products of Reactions.—Nitrites were detected with Griess reagent. Traces of nitrates were detected with phenoldisulphonic acid test colorimetrically. Hydroxylamine salt solution (5 c.c.) gave nitrite as shown below when estimated colorimetrically by Griess reagent method (diazo method).

TABLE V

Salt	Conc. per litre	Nitrite obs.	Nitrite reqd. as per sqn.
$\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$	1/150 M	1.49 mg.	1.53 mg.
$(\text{NH}_2\text{OH})_2.\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$	1/320	1.41	1.44
$\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HNO}_3$	1/200	1.12	1.15

The hydroxylamine nitrate required for this work was prepared by the method of Lossen (Mellor, "Treatise on Theoretical and Inorganic Chemistry" Vol. VIII, p. 303). Berthelot and Andrew (*Compt. rend.*, 1890, 11, 95) tried to prepare hydroxylamine nitrate by double decomposition but could obtain only a viscid liquid. The solution was concentrated over phosphorous pentoxide in a vacuum desiccator. The viscid liquid so obtained when cooled in a freezing mixture gave a white crystalline solid which was kept in a desiccator over phosphorous pentoxide. It is a white crystalline substance, extremely hygroscopic and decomposes spontaneously, more so under reduced pressure.

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